

Kinetics of Complexing of Aquachromium(III) by L-Proline

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In continuation of our studies on aquachromium(III)/amino acid systems¹, we present herein investigations with L-proline (an α -imino acid) in order to provide more data on the reactivity and mechanism of $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$. Our approach is different from other workers in the following two ways: (i) to confirm existence of outer-sphere association equilibrium, additional kinetic runs were performed in water-ethanol mixed solvents in order to observe the effect of the dielectric constant (D) on the reaction rate, and, (ii) in support of a common associative interchange mechanism for the anation of hexaaquachromium(III) by a series of amino acids, including the L-proline, an argument based on isokinetic correlation among activation parameters is presented.

Results and Discussion

In the present system (acidity range, $6.5 \leq 10^4 [\text{H}^+] \leq 36.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) the reactive species are $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ and ProH and the reaction can be represented by equation (1),

Values of k_{obs} obtained under varying sets of experimental conditions are given in Table I. The rate increases with increase in $[\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}$, $[\text{proline}]_{\text{T}}$, %EtOH, ionic strength and temperature but decreases with increase in $[\text{H}^+]$. As the $[\text{proline}]_{\text{T}}$ increases, k_{obs} increases in a non-linear manner and, at higher $[\text{proline}]_{\text{T}}$, appears to reach a limiting

value. Such behaviour indicates formation of an outer-sphere association complex (OSC) between the reactive species². The OSC is formed very rapidly wherein the ligand occupies a site in the immediate vicinity of the metal ion and then in a rate-controlling step, the ligand molecule occupies the site vacated by the leaving water molecule. The OSC concentration in solution increases with the increase in ligand concentration. At last, at a certain ligand concentration, the formation of OSC is complete and a limit is reached. Any further addition of the ligand does not influence the OSC concentration and instead increases the amount of the ligand in bulk solution. This does not have any effect on k_{obs} .

The following mechanism, consistent with the data, is proposed for which the k_{obs} is given by equation (5).

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_1 K_{\text{OS}} K_a [\text{proline}]_{\text{T}}}{[\text{H}^+] + K_a + K_{\text{OS}} K_a [\text{proline}]_{\text{T}}} \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) can be rearranged to

$$k_{\text{obs}}^{-1} = 1/k_1 + A/B [\text{proline}]_{\text{T}}^{-1} \quad (6)$$

TABLE I—VALUES OF PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k_{obs}) FOR THE ANATION OF HEXAAQUACHROMIUM(III) BY L-PROLINE

Temp. °C	$\times 10^4 [\text{H}^+]$ mol dm ⁻³	$\times 10^2 [\text{proline}]_{\text{T}} \text{ (mol dm}^{-3}\text{)}$						$\times 10^4 k_1$ s ⁻¹	K_{OS} mol ⁻¹ dm ³	$\times 10^3 K_a$ mol dm ⁻³
		4.0	6.0	8.0	10.0	12.0	16.0			
45	36.3	0.56	0.80	0.99	1.22	1.30	1.67	4.0	7.2	11.13
	11.5	0.79	0.94	1.20	1.39	1.54	1.82			
	6.5	0.92	1.24	1.42	1.72	1.90	2.08			
50	36.3	0.63	0.92	1.13	1.39	1.42	1.79	5.0	7.0	10.96
	11.5	0.93	1.18	1.48	1.71	1.72	2.41			
	6.5	1.11	1.50	1.94	2.09	2.33	2.70			
55	36.3	0.79	1.02	1.52	1.61	1.96	2.29	6.7	6.6	10.73
	11.5	1.02	1.39	1.71	2.13	2.30	2.58			
	6.5	1.32	1.79	2.22	2.70	2.62	2.95			
60	36.3	1.20	1.64	2.13	2.50	2.78	3.03	10.0	5.3	10.45
	11.5	1.49	2.00	2.63	2.94	3.13	3.45			
	6.5	1.75	2.17	2.94	3.57	3.70	4.35			

with $A = [H^+] + K_a$, and $B = k_i K_{OS} K_a$. Equation (6) envisages linearity in the plots of k_{obs}^{-1} vs $[proline]_T^{-1}$ at constant acidity with a common intercept ($=1/k_i$) for all $[H^+]$. The experimental results confirm this criterion. The values of anation rate-constant (k_i) and outer-sphere association constants (K_{OS}) were evaluated by least-squares regression analysis of the data (Table 1) along with activation parameters which were obtained by plotting $\ln k_i N h / RT$ against $1/T$.

Like charges on $[Cr(H_2O)_6]^{3+}$ and protonated L-proline ($ProH_2^+$) are unfavourable for outer-sphere association and therefore, such steps are excluded from the mechanism. Although the net charge on the proline zwitterion is zero, it has a separated negative charge on the carboxylate part and can form outer-sphere association complexes with multivalent cations. Since the variation in λ_m for different chromium(III)-amino acid systems is not large¹, one can infer that in all these cases the bonding between chromium and the amino acids is of a similar nature. Thus, in conformity to the structures assigned to other metal ion-amino acid complexes in solutions at $pH < 4^3$, coordination of the zwitterionic proline $^-OOC-R-NH_2^+$ to chromium(III) metal center through its O-end seems most plausible. Also, chelation is unfavoured where amino (or imino) group of the amino acid is protonated⁴; in the present case, even if it does take place it must be fast and not rate-limiting as can be inferred from the following: (i) reactions follow a pseudo-first order process, and, (ii) the present results are comparable with those for monodentate carboxylic ligand acetic acid⁵.

The observed increase in rate with increasing % EtOH ($10^4 k_{obs}$: 1.42, 1.64, 2.25, 2.84, 3.63, 4.23, 5.04 s^{-1} respectively at 0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30% EtOH) produced a linear plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $1/D$ with a positive slope. This further supports that the reaction is of ion-dipole type. Obviously, according to Bjerrum's equation⁶, the K_{OS} value would increase with the decrease in D (as the forces of attraction between the species increase) and therefore, OSC formation is enhanced with a consequent rate increase.

A comparison of isotopic water-exchange rate (k_{ex}) with that of anation rate constant (k_i) has been utilised as a means for distinguishing intimate mechanisms. For an associative interchange (I_a) process k_i should vary markedly with the nucleophilic power of the incoming ligand towards M^{n+} , and where this power is high, it actually exceeds k_{ex} ; whereas for a dissociative interchange (I_d) process, k_i should be less or equal to k_{ex} ⁷. It is clear from Table 1, as the k_i values of the present system are far greater than k_{ex} ($=10 \times 10^{-6} s^{-1}$ for $Cr(H_2O)_6^{3+}/O^{18}H_2$ at 35°)⁸, that the transformation of the outer- into the inner-sphere complex is associatively activated. A much lower ΔH^\ddagger value (+55 kJ mol^{-1}) than for the isotopic water-exchange (108.6 kJ

mol^{-1}) suggests significant bond formation by ProH in the transition state in the transformation of OSC. Pronounced participation of the incoming ligand in the transition state is confirmed further by the observed large negative ΔS^\ddagger value ($-136 kJ mol^{-1} K^{-1}$ as compared to $+11.65 J mol^{-1} K^{-1}$ for the water-exchange). Thus, associative character of $[Cr(H_2O)_6]^{3+}$ and L-proline reaction is confirmed on the basis of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger values also. Furthermore, reactions that follow common mechanisms show an isokinetic relationship, $\Delta H^\ddagger = C + D \Delta S^\ddagger$. A plot of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger for some hexaaquachromium(III)/amino acid reactions is fairly linear which confirms, like all other hexaaquachromium(III) reactions, the I_a assignment to the title reaction.

The formation of OSC seems to be responsible for the dependence of k_{obs} on μ ($10^4 k_{obs}$: 1.33, 1.37, 1.38, 1.38, 1.42 s^{-1} respectively, at 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0 $mol dm^{-3}$). On addition of excess nitrate, reorientation of the coordinated water molecules (in the OSCs) around NO_3^- (through H-bonding) takes place. As a result, Cr-OH₂ bonds are weakened and thus removal of coordinated water molecules from the OSCs is facilitated by nitrate ions. Later, these water molecules are engaged to form a solvation sheath for nitrate ions.

Experimental

L-Proline (puriss, Koch-light) was used. Chromium(III) solution was prepared from $Cr(NO_3)_3 \cdot 9H_2O$ (A.R., Ortnal, Italy).

In acidic solutions, L-proline reacted with chromium(III) to form a purple complex that exhibits absorption maxima at 420 and 570 nm. Spectrophotometric measurements performed on equilibrated mixtures of the reactants (prepared according to Job's method of continuous variations) showed the composition of the complex to be 1 : 1.

All the kinetic runs were performed with proline ($= (4-16) \times 10^{-2} mol dm^{-3}$) in excess with respect to Cr^{III} ($= (3-8) \times 10^{-3} mol dm^{-3}$). Solutions of the required final pH were made up by mixing deoxygenated and thermally equilibrated stock solutions of the reactants that contained calculated amounts of HNO_3 or $NaOH$ and KNO_3 . Progress of the reaction was monitored by following the complex formation at 570 nm. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were obtained by linear least-squares regression analysis.

A Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer and an Elico LI-120 pH meter were used.

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